
Common Errors in Word order among Uzbek Learners of English a Contrastive Perspective

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Annotation *The article focuses on examining common word order mistakes made by Uzbek learners of English based on contrastive analysis. The importance of learning word order is that it directly affects grammatically correct and clear communication in a foreign language. English and Uzbek languages belong to different language families and sentence structure is a main component of all sentences. As a result, students have difficulties in using syntactic structures correctly when composing sentences in English. Both languages have different syntactic structures and this difference leads to errors in language learners. It is widely acknowledged that Uzbek language mainly follows SOV (Subject-object-verb) word order, and the English language is SVO (Subject-verb-object) structure. This structural difference is one of the main reasons for negative transfer in second language acquisition. This main difference causes learners to transfer native patterns from native language into English. The study analyzes their typical errors, explains their causes and suggests pedagogical strategies to reduce the errors encountered in language learning. The results of the research serve to improve the teaching methodology and increase students' understanding of the syntactic differences between the two languages.*

Keywords *Word order, analytic language, relatively fixed, flexible, native language, errors, sentence structure*

O'zbek tilida so'zlashuvchi ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilarda so'z tartibi bilan bog'liq keng tarqalgan xatolar: kontrastiv tahlil yondashuvi asosida tadqiqot

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Annotatsiya *Ushbu maqola kontrastiv tahlil asosida o'zbek tilida so'zlashuvchi ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilarda uchraydigan so'z tartibi bilan bog'liq keng tarqalgan xatolarni o'rganishga qaratilgan. So'z tartibini o'rganishning ahamiyati shundaki, u chet tilida grammatik jihatdan to'g'ri va aniq muloqot qilishga bevosita ta'sir qiladi. Ingliz va o'zbek tillari turli til oilalariga mansub bo'lib, gap tuzilishi barcha gaplarning asosiy tarkibiy qismi hisoblanadi. Natijada, o'quvchilar ingliz tilida gap tuzishda sintaktik tuzilmalardan to'g'ri foydalanishda qiyinchiliklarga duch keladilar. Bu ikki tilning sintaktik tuzilmalari bir-biridan farq qiladi va bu farq til o'rganuvchilarda xatolarga olib keladi. Ma'lumki, o'zbek tili asosan SOV (ega-to'ldiruvchi-kesim) so'z tartibiga,*

ingliz tili esa SVO (ega-kesim-to'ldiruvchi) tuzilishiga amal qiladi. Ushbu tuzilmaviy farq ikkinchi tilni o'zlashtirish jarayonida salbiy transferning asosiy sabablaridan biridir. Bu farq o'quvchilarning ona tilidagi grammatik naqshlarni ingliz tiliga ko'chirishiga olib keladi. Tadqiqot o'quvchilarda uchraydigan tipik xatolarni tahlil qiladi, ularning sabablarini tushuntiradi hamda til o'rganish jarayonida uchraydigan xatolarni kamaytirish uchun pedagogik strategiyalarni taklif qiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirishga va o'quvchilarning ikki til o'rtasidagi sintaktik farqlar haqidagi tushunchasini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar *So'z tartibi, analitik til, nisbatan qat'iy, moslashuvchan, ona tili, xatolar, gap tuzilishi*

Распространённые ошибки в порядке слов у узбекских учащихся английского языка: исследование с позиции контрастивного анализа

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Аннотация *Данная статья направлена на изучение распространённых ошибок в порядке слов, которые допускают узбекские учащиеся при изучении английского языка, на основе контрастивного анализа. Важность изучения порядка слов заключается в том, что он напрямую влияет на грамматически правильное и понятное общение на иностранном языке. Английский и узбекский языки относятся к разным языковым семьям, а структура предложения является основным компонентом любого высказывания. В результате учащиеся испытывают трудности при правильном использовании синтаксических структур при построении предложений на английском языке. Оба языка имеют разные синтаксические структуры, и это различие приводит к ошибкам у изучающих язык. Известно, что узбекский язык в основном следует порядку слов SOV (подлежащее-дополнение-сказуемое), а английский язык – структуре SVO (подлежащее-сказуемое-дополнение). Это структурное различие является одной из основных причин негативного переноса в процессе овладения вторым языком. Данное различие приводит к тому, что учащиеся переносят модели родного языка в английскую речь. В исследовании анализируются типичные ошибки учащихся, объясняются их причины и предлагаются педагогические стратегии для их уменьшения. Результаты исследования способствуют совершенствованию методики преподавания и повышению понимания учащимися синтаксических различий между двумя языками.*

Ключевые слова *Порядок слов, аналитический язык, относительно фиксированный, гибкий, родной язык, ошибки, структура предложения*

Introduction

In some languages word order is relatively fixed, while some languages word order is moveable. If the words are rearranged, the sentence may lose its original meaning. In Uzbek word order is very flexible due to its rich system of suffixes while, in English it is fixed. This difference creates significant difficulties for students to construct correct sentences in English. Differences in the use of verbs and adverbs are beneficial for learners of these languages, as they have less difficulty with correct use of word order. Also, these differences are of great help not only for language learners, but also in the translation process.

The major process of this article is:

- Identify common errors in Word order.
- Analyzing them by contrastive analysis.
- Provide methodological recommendations.

These objectives facilitate a deeper understanding of issues related to language acquisition. Furthermore, this research contributes to the more effective organization of the teaching process.

In analytic languages such as English, the sequence of words is frequently crucial for achieving clear and unambiguous communication. Words are arranged according to established patterns and frameworks that define their relationships and functions within a sentence. In English word order is rigid, which follows the Subject-verb-object. (SVO) model (Swan&Smith, 2001). In English, word order plays a crucial role in determining grammatical function. That is why the order of words in English is grammatically fixed and cannot be changed. In this structure, the subject appears first, followed by the verb and then the object. For instance, in the sentence "Nancy cleans the room every morning", "Nancy" functions as a subject, "cleans" is a verb, and "the room" is an object. Therefore, the position of each word determines the syntactic structure of the

sentence. In addition, word order plays a significant role in English, because if the arrangement of words are changed, the meaning of the sentence will also change or be grammatically incorrect. The accuracy of sentence structure in English ensures the effectiveness of communication. Therefore, learners should pay particular attention to word order.

In contrast, in Uzbek grammatical relations rely on morphological structures and correct use of suffixes. Uzbek usually follows Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) order: *Malika xonanitozalaydi* (*Malika cleans the room*). This allows students to construct sentences in different word order, and this situation leads to mistakes in learning English. The correct use of grammatical adverbs such as possessives, adverbs, and verb forms make the sentence clearer. Word order in a sentence mainly indicates stylistic purpose and flexibility. For example, the object marker *-ni* explicitly indicates the grammatical role of the noun in a sentence, so the sentence can be rearranged without losing meaning: *Xonani Malika tozalaydi*. The study of languages belong to the two contrasting families is important for language learners and linguistics. Differences in word order constitute one of the most prevalent challenges in the process of language learning. The rigid structural framework of the English language presents considerable difficulty for Uzbek learners. This characteristic renders the Uzbek language both flexible and expressive. However, this very flexibility creates challenges in the acquisition of English. Through this approach, students' errors can be anticipated in advance. This difference more clearly demonstrates the structural contrast between the two languages. As a result, teachers are able to plan lessons more effectively.

Common word order mistakes

Comparative analysis is a linguistic approach that includes systematically

comparing two languages to analyze differences and similarities and predict learning difficulties. This theory identifies differences between the learner's native language and the target language are one of the main sources of errors in second language acquisition (Lado, 1957; Ellis, 2008). One of the main differences between Uzbek and English lies in their word order patterns. The Uzbek language is characterized by flexible word order. In response, English has a stricter and more rigid word order. Because of this structural difference, Uzbek learners often transfer native language patterns to English, which leads to various errors. This phenomenon is commonly called language interference or negative transfer (Odlin, 1989; Selinker, 1972). Such interference prevents students from fully mastering the new language system. As a result, students often rely on their mother tongue and form an incorrect model.

Verb placement errors

Learners often make mistakes related to word order in English and Uzbek. The most common mistakes are related to incorrect placement of the verb, violation of the order of adverbs, failure to use auxiliary verbs in interrogative sentences, incorrect construction of negative forms, and incorrect placement of expressions of time and place. For example, *he a book reads* instead of *he reads a book* as a verb placement error. Also, in interrogative sentences *you are coming?* instead of *are you coming?* form should be used. These errors mainly occur as a result of transferring the freer and SOV-type sentence structure of the Uzbek language to the English language and also it is directly related to the fact that the verb in Uzbek comes at the end of the sentence. Verb placement errors indicate that students have not yet fully mastered English grammar and these errors occur particularly frequently at the initial stage of learning. This problem is associated with the incorrect acquisition of the predicate structure in English.

Adverb placement errors

In Uzbek, adverbs are relatively free, but in English their place in a sentence is subject to clear rules. Because of this, language learners tend to misplace adverbs within the sentence. For example, *I every day go to university*, instead of *I go to university every day* is correct. This shows that the students have not yet been able to adapt to the strict order of the English language. Incorrect placement vowels results in speech that sounds unnatural. This negatively affects the fluency of speech. Incorrect placement of adverbs reduces the stylistic quality of the sentence.

Question formation errors

Interrogative sentences in English require an auxiliary verb and inversion, while in Uzbek, intonation or prepositions are often sufficient. Because of this difference, students make mistakes. For example, *You are coming?* instead of *Are you coming?* is used. As a result, student cannot fully use the system of auxiliary verbs in English. These errors arise due to an insufficient understanding of question structures in English. The use of auxiliary verbs is particularly challenging for learners. This situation requires the mastery of inversion rules in English.

Negation errors

In English, negative sentences are formed using auxiliary verbs, but in Uzbek, this system is different. As a result, students use incorrect forms. For example, instead of *I go not to school*, *I do not go to school* is correct. These errors are also explained by the complexity of negative forms in English. Errors in negative constructions may lead to misunderstanding of sentence meaning. Therefore, this issue requires special attention. Because, such mistakes have a negative impact on communicative accuracy.

Placement of time and Place expressions

In English, expressions of time and place usually come at the end of the sentence, while in Uzbek they have a freer place. This leads to errors. For example, *I to Samarkand yesterday went*, instead of *I went to Samarkand yesterday*.

These errors disrupt the logical structure of the sentence. Consequently, it becomes difficult to comprehend the sentence. Auxiliary verbs serve an essential grammatical function in English. Their omission renders the sentence grammatically incorrect. This rule serves to ensure pragmatic accuracy in English.

Auxiliary verb errors

Many grammatical constructions in English require auxiliary verbs. Since there is no such system in the Uzbek language, students leave them down. For example, instead of *She not know*, *She does not know* is correct (Swan&Smith, 2001). Their correct use ensures the grammatical completeness of the sentence.

Causes of errors

Errors related to word order are mainly explained by several factors. The main reason is the influence of the mother tongue, and learners copy the structure of sentences in Uzbek to English. In addition, insufficient understanding of English syntax is also one of the important factors. Another reason is overgeneralization, where students incorrectly apply one grammatical rule to other situations. Auxiliary verbs serve an essential grammatical function in English.

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Pedagogical implications

To reduce these errors, teachers need to use several effective methods. First of all, it is important to explain the differences between

English and Uzbek in a clear and understandable way. Also, regular exercises should be given to teach students to construct correct sentences, especially exercises on SVO structure, interrogative sentences, and placement of adverbs. Correcting errors in time and explaining the reason is also of great importance. In addition, it is recommended to develop students' practical skills through the use of visual aids such as diagrams and charts, and through role-plays and dialogue-based activities. The application of modern methods enhances students' interest. This significantly improves the effectiveness of learning. These approaches help to develop stable grammatical competence in students.

Differences in word order between English and Uzbek languages are one of the important difficulties for Uzbek learners. As discussed in this article, the differences between the strict SVO structure of English and the relatively loose SOV order of Uzbek cause many errors. In particular, the wrong location of the verb, the order of verbs, the wrong structure of interrogative and negative sentences, and the omission of auxiliary verbs appear as the most common errors. These errors are mainly caused by the influence of the mother tongue, insufficient grammatical knowledge and incorrect generalization (Richards, 1974). Therefore, it is important to use a contrastive approach in teaching English, that is, to clearly show the differences between the two languages. The findings of this study are also valuable for future research. Moreover, these results can be applied in practical teaching contexts. In general, the language learning process requires a systematic approach.

In conclusion, the differences between the word order in English and Uzbek are one of the most significant challenges in the process of language learning. In English, word order is relatively strict, but in Uzbek it is more free, which causes mistakes in students. The analysis shows that the main cause of word order errors is the influence of the mother tongue and

insufficient mastery of grammatical rules. As a result, the structure of the sentence is broken and it becomes difficult to express the idea clearly. In order to form the correct word order in students, along with theoretical

explanations, it is necessary to use practical exercises, continuous corrections, and effective communication methods. This will help students to develop the skills of making correct and fluent sentences in English.

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